

Cruise log SR2527- SR2601
December 13th 2025- January 15th 2026
Rocio Rodriguez Perez – Sem Docekal (Amy after leg 3)

Funding:

OCE-2419287: Ship Operations for Research Vessel SALLY RIDE
OCE-2127538, OCE-2127524, OCE-2127299: Collaborative Research: Metabolic habitat barriers imposed on tropical diel vertical migrators

Legs:

SR2527 (leg 1, transit to La Paz) – December 13th to 18th 2025
SR2528 (leg 2, first science leg) – December 18th 2025 to January 29th 2026
SR2529 (leg 3, second science leg) – January 29 to January 6th 2026
SR2601 (leg 4, transit to San Diego) – January 6 to January 14th 2026

December 13th (SR2527)

Finish setting up the MOCNESS; all issues have been fixed. Review the MOCNESS computer system with Amy. Ensure everything is secured and tied down. Safety briefing at 18:30hrs.

December 14th (SR2527)

Assembled part of the tucker trawl. Abandon ship drill. Started puzzle.

December 15th (SR2527)

Set up respiration system. Adjusted and printed mocness and respiration data sheets. Finished puzzle.

December 16th (SR2527)

Discussed Cruise project

December 17th (SR2527)

Prepared reeve net. Started water baths. Printed Safety Data Sheets. Put “dip net” together.

December 18th (SR2528)

Arrived at La Paz 8:00hs. Welcomed new cruise members. Depart to Guaymas 16:00hs. Safety Brief meeting at 18:00hs. Re arrange and set up lab spaces.

December 19th (SR2528)

Meeting with amy 8:00hs, discussed MOCNESS calibration. Science meeting 9:00hs. Wire Flyer test deployment at 10:20hs. Preparation of acid and mili q bath. Set up pump on formalin bottle. Drill 12:15hs. Sem and Ro prepared and deployed CTD. Depths were selected with Ana. Filter water for Shannon Doherty. Target depths were 20m (6L), 350 (7L), 550 (14L). Also, filtered water for respirations. There was some jiggling!

NISKIN	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
DEPTH	1000	1000	900	900	800	800	600	600	550	550	400	400	350	350	300	300	280	280	200	200	100	50	20	20
Shannon									X	X			X	X									X	X
Ana	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		

December 20th (SR2528)

Dive 830am (low visibility), after that MOCNESS deployment for the first vertical D/N pair. Decided not to do a calibration. MOCNESS was prepared in san diego during mob day. We first did a deck test: the net tripped, and we received a net response (MOC 1). However, during the deployment (MOC 2) we didn't get a net response back, so we manually tripped twice and manually confirmed the rest. When the net came up, none of the nets had opened. The nets were cocked the other way around (from center to outside), not forming a V. We fixed the issue, cocked correctly and prepped for next tow. After some deliberation we concluded that the plan was to continue with the MOCNESS night deployment as planned and re-do the day tow next morning. Night MOCNESS deployment was successful. Fow meter 1 not working so we are using flow meter 2 as primary. Samples were processed in both formalin and ethanol. Sem and Ro processed the formalin portion and provided Ana with the proportional part of the sample for ethanol preservation. Sem and Ro Prepped the moc for tomorrow's early deployment. Wire flyer was deployed after mocness retrieval.

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251221	35333	1	1	634	1406.53	999.7	4.772	33.2973	34.54	0.03	95.9	0.1	46.2
251221	41306	2	2	243	489.53	903.3	5.11	33.5516	34.532	0.03	95.71	0.055	54.7
251221	51126	3	3	682	1603.83	500.1	8.718	36.7326	34.607	0.01	95.92	0.006	44.2
251221	52837	4	4	163	405.27	392.9	10.052	37.9799	34.658	0.01	95.92	0.024	41
251221	53545	5	5	74	190.54	324.7	10.833	38.7368	34.71	0	95.92	0.07	37.4
251221	54447	6	6	104	261.64	224.7	12.235	40.1258	34.806	0	23.75	0.264	40.9
251221	55327	7	7	87	206.44	150.2	13.606	41.5391	34.923	0.03	23.56	0.713	44.2
251221	55853	8	8	55	128.83	109.9	14.644	42.5848	34.971	0	23.46	0.941	46.7
251221	60421	9	9	63	145.51	70.3	16.508	44.4901	35.044	0.03	23.3	1.338	46.9
251221	61444	10	10	116	276.35	-0.2	20.595	0.4382	0.232	-0.05	85.77	6.388	19.4

December 21th (SR2528)

8:00 Dive followed by vertical day MOCNESS (#5), smooth deployment and retrieval. Provided Ana with 1/2 of the sample of each cod end to preserve in Ethanol. Tucker trawl at 300m from which we selected 12 Pteropods of different groups to respire, all successful. CTD went in at night to 1900m, water was collected from the deepest bottle for respirations.

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251221	184157	1	1	479	1280.47	999.6	4.614	33.1595	34.544	0.03	95.92	0.117	30.8
251221	185527	2	2	150	363.81	899.7	5.172	33.6044	34.531	0.02	95.92	0.05	42.2
251221	194837	3	3	560	1177.71	499.9	8.527	36.5454	34.596	0.01	95.76	0.002	53.4
251221	200343	4	4	201	417.33	401	9.662	37.5978	34.637	0	95.66	0.011	53.5
251221	201537	5	5	151	319.85	324.5	10.93	38.8375	34.718	0	95.69	0.083	53.6
251221	202658	6	6	159	301.71	225.9	12.448	40.3627	34.837	0	23.67	0.38	58.4
251221	204308	7	7	222	444.65	150.4	13.841	41.7839	34.939	0	23.51	0.765	55.1
251221	204912	8	8	79	167.29	110.4	14.943	42.9063	34.996	0	23.42	1.059	52.2
251221	205439	9	9	70	150.29	69.7	17.061	45.072	35.072	-0.01	23.28	1.455	52.1
251221	210351	10	10	114	273.37	-0.2	20.289	0.4188	0.223	-0.03	89.97	6.276	21.1

December 22th (SR2528)

8:00 Dive, followed by 2 back-to-back Tucker trawls (350m & 1200m). Broke down exp1 (pteropods) respiration, took photos off all and saved in 4% formalin. First tucker was full of myctophids, we set-up 12 Ostracods from the 350m Tucker for respiration, good signal on all. Gathering on the bow to watch sunset, socializing time! Followed by a science meeting with a presentation from

Wireflyer team and Amy on WhatsApp call.

Decisions were made to do horizontal MOCNESS to target the transition between in- and outside the eddy. Loki went in at night followed by Wireflyer.

Rest of the night was spent planning where and what to aim for during the horizontal tow the next day.

December 23th (SR2528)

8:00 Dive, 3 salps set apart for Lloyd in tripours. Broke down Exp2 (ostracods) respirations, took photos of all and preserved in 4% formalin in cryovials. Followed by Horizontal day MOCNESS (10:20) targeting the transition of the eddy at 275m depth. Smooth deployment and retrieval. Results indicate that we captured what we aimed for, a portion outside the eddy, the transition and a portion inside the eddy, hopefully.

Tucker trawl after the day MOC6 followed by LOKI and another MOCNESS targeting the same transition backwards and shifted north (following the feature) at night (20:00). Again, the results indicate what we aimed for with biomass inside the eddy, very little in the transition and higher biomass again outside the eddy. The horizontal tows are limited to net 1-8, in the night MOCNESS (MOC7) net 8 was towed for 10 minutes but showed a ridiculous amount of biomass, net response light stayed on for a long time when triggering net 8 which might indicate the net got stuck at the response, stayed open and filtered far more time/distance/depth. WireFlier went in after the MOCNESS, following the same transect (?). After processing the night MOCNESS we photographed Lloyds salps, collected the poops in 15m falcon tubes and set up respirations for the 3 salps, somewhat questionable, will need to check.

MOC 6

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251223	180231	1	1	230	529.4	274.7	11.028	38.9142	34.725	0.01	23.82	0.087	43.1
251223	181948	2	2	184	383.15	274.7	11.222	39.1169	34.743	0	23.82	0.127	50.8
251223	183129	3	3	122	262.09	275.8	11.185	39.0871	34.748	0	23.82	0.171	51
251223	185352	4	4	237	521.76	274.5	11.342	39.243	34.755	0	23.7	0.159	50.5
251223	192200	5	5	298	628.98	274.7	11.296	39.2076	34.764	0	23.68	0.197	51.1
251223	195134	6	6	332	686.24	274.9	11.455	39.3747	34.779	0	23.75	0.281	53.1
251223	201711	7	7	300	638.76	276	11.313	39.2137	34.753	0.01	23.77	0.154	52.1
251223	204643	8	8	344	739.44	275.9	11.34	39.2422	34.755	0	23.75	0.154	50.9
251223	210623	9	9	226	466.48	275.4	11.419	39.3254	34.764	0	23.77	0.184	52.1
251223	214108	10	10	459	1116.16	-0.3	21.166	0.1622	0.086	-0.03	78.12	6.253	17.4

MOC 7

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251224	41010	1	1	360	824.57	274.4	11.381	39.2819	34.757	-0.01	23.75	0.158	46.2
251224	42310	2	2	133	288.31	275.4	11.443	39.3603	34.776	0.02	23.69	0.243	48.8
251224	44208	3	3	189	426.76	275.4	11.442	39.3642	34.781	0	23.75	0.281	47.6
251224	51954	4	4	372	835.53	275.4	11.356	39.2527	34.751	-0.01	23.72	0.133	48.5
251224	52944	5	5	97	214.15	274.8	11.236	39.1292	34.742	0	23.79	0.116	48.8
251224	53827	6	6	85	195.61	274.1	11.247	39.1561	34.759	0	23.77	0.21	47.5
251224	55812	7	7	194	445.7	274.7	11.563	39.4888	34.79	0.01	23.72	0.322	46.7
251224	61016	8	8	116	274.39	279.5	11.345	39.2645	34.771	0.01	23.75	0.261	45.9
251224	63212	9	9	215	491.95	275.9	11.257	39.1781	34.771	0.01	23.75	0.269	48.1
251224	70855	10	10	464	790.46	47.6	20.515	48.8861	35.343	0.1	22.75	3.71	56.6

MOC6, Net 1
275m,
VF=383.2

MOC6, Net 2
275m,
VF=262.1

MOC6, Net 3
275m,
VF=521.8

MOC6, Net 4
275m,
VF=629

MOC6, Net 5
275m,
VF=686.2

MOC6, Net 6
275m,
638.8

MOC6, Net 7
275m,
VF=739.4

MOC6, Net 8
275m,
VF=466.5

Tow 3 (MOC6)
Day tow
Horizontal
275m
10:30-14:42
12-22-25

December 24th (SR2528)

8:00 Dive followed by a Tucker trawl, MOCNESS (MOC8) went in at 13:00 for a day fine scale. Minor issues during the first half of the tow finding the right balance between net speed, boat speed and net angle. Boat speed fluctuates a bit more than desired but 1.8knts at 4MPM wire in seems like the best target for fine scale MOCNESS. Samples were processed and tucker trawl went for another trawl while science and crew did Karaoke! LOKI was deployed around 21:00 followed by squid jigging which gave Arminda her 5 MASSIVE squid. At 22:00 MOCNESS (MOC9) went in for the night fine scale targeting the same depths as during the day, much smoother flying with minor adjustments. Retrieving the net from the surface was slightly delayed which might impact the accuracy of volume filtered for net 9 but this was probably the least important net. Night samples were processed and Lloyds Salp respirations broken down, all 3 reached Pcrit and were saved in -80.

MOC8, Net 1
425-375m
VF=310.5

MOC8, Net 2
375-350m,
VF=283.6

MOC8, Net 3
350-325m,
VF=90.5

MOC8, Net 4
325-275m,
VF=90.8

MOC8, Net 5
275-250m.,
VF=512.2

MOC8, Net 6
250-225m,
VF=190.8

MOC8, Net 7
225-200m,
VF=232.4

MOC8, Net 8
200-125m,
VF=267.2

MOC8, Net 9
125-0m,
VF=267.2

Tow 5 (MOC8)
Day tow
Fine scale
13:30-15:30
12-24-25

MOC9, Net 1
425-375m,
VF=285.9

MOC9, Net 2
375-350m,
VF=165.9

MOC9, Net 3
350-325m,
VF=265.2

MOC9, Net 4
325-275m,
VF=195.9

MOC9, Net 5
275-250m,
VF=198.8

MOC9, Net 6
250-225m,
VF=306.3

MOC9, Net 7
225-200m,
VF=164.6

MOC9, Net 8
200-125m,
VF=296.3

MOC9, Net 9
125-0m,
VF=362.3

Tow 6 (MOC9)
Night tow
Fine scale
22:30-00:30
12-24-25

MOC8-D

MOC9-N

MOC 8

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251224	205457	1	1	107	310.51	424.7	9.01	36.9497	34.585	0.01	95.92	-99	21.3
251224	210519	2	2	101	283.55	372.2	10.026	37.9604	34.673	0	95.92	0.055	28.4
251224	210758	3	3	34	90.48	347.5	10.235	38.1512	34.678	0.01	95.92	0.061	32.2
251224	211042	4	4	36	90.8	323.3	10.727	38.6433	34.717	0.01	95.92	0.114	37.7
251224	213110	5	5	205	512.24	274	11.482	39.3919	34.771	0	23.79	0.209	39.6
251224	213943	6	6	77	190.77	250.4	11.878	39.7747	34.786	0	23.74	0.198	40.6
251224	215015	7	7	92	232.42	225.2	12.352	40.2542	34.822	0	23.67	0.319	39.3
251224	220205	8	8	102	267.22	200.1	12.927	40.8502	34.873	0	23.58	0.502	35.7
251224	221507	9	9	124	324.67	124.5	14.967	42.9288	34.99	0	23.33	0.974	36.4
251224	223125	10	10	172	411.53	-0.2	20.124	0.1087	0.06	-0.02	86.82	6.412	5.5

MOC 9

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251225	61005	1	1	435	970.02	425	8.911	36.8743	34.602	0.01	95.85	0.002	45.7
251225	62237	2	2	138	285.91	375.3	9.621	37.5336	34.623	0	95.71	0.006	53.5
251225	62939	3	3	81	165.88	350.3	10.069	37.9696	34.65	0	95.67	0.006	54.2
251225	64031	4	4	123	265.16	325.1	10.719	38.6293	34.71	0.02	95.69	0.08	52.9
251225	64833	5	5	99	195.9	275.1	11.619	39.5271	34.775	0.02	23.63	0.203	56.1
251225	65629	6	6	96	198.75	255.3	11.842	39.749	34.792	0	23.56	0.244	54.7
251225	70852	7	7	145	306.34	225.1	12.487	40.4068	34.844	0	23.56	0.413	53.1
251225	71522	8	8	76	164.65	200.5	12.91	40.8383	34.877	0	23.51	0.525	52.8
251225	72626	9	9	136	296.28	119.3	14.776	42.7043	34.958	0	23.32	0.907	51.8
251225	73934	10	10	152	362.32	-0.2	21.196	49.6234	35.389	1.18	95.85	4.838	40

MOC 8-D

December 25th (SR2528)

8:00 Dive, followed by 300-260 tucker, we picked out 3 salps for Lloyd from the tucker which were placed in tri-pours and 12 copepods for our respirations. At night we had Christmas dinner with crew and science as well as ‘white elephant’ gift exchange. The reeve net went in for the first time after dinner to 100m and we collected 7? more salps which were each placed in individual tri-pours. All salps will be placed in Lloyds respiration plungers in the morning. We caught up with paperwork.

December 26th (SR2528)

No diving this morning due to bad conditions, transit to Carmen during the night. Most salps we put in Tripours overnight died, only one was in good enough shape to start respirations on. We broke down the copepod respirations imaged them and stored them away. Tucker went in in the morning 10:30 (500m wire out). 12 amphipods were selected from the

tucker trawl for respirations (experiment 4). 3 more salps were collected from the tucker and put in tri-pours for Lloyd. Wire flyer went in for a day deployment around 1 pm. MOCNESS deployed at night 20:00, rough sea and winds forced the ship to maintain speeds of +2 knots, mainly driven by currents as the ship barely had the engines running. After calling the bridge we mostly maintained an acceptable speed under 2.5 knots but at net 3 the only working flowmeter gave out and we were flying with 2 flowmeters measuring 0's. At this point we decided the tow wasn't quantitative and could be considered failed but due to still maintaining high ship speeds of 2-2.5 knts we decided not to pull the net in quicker (ship could not be slowed down further since engines weren't the driving factor).

Upon retrieval the flowmeters were visibly spinning (the issue is in the props not connecting to the gears) but besides that, all the nets were tangled up, currents and waves probably being the cause. All nets (including 0) were practically empty indicating being tangled on the way down. Retrieval was another issue caused by wind, bad slacklining and the MOC rolling off the deck bending one of the metal brackets holding the fluor/temp/transmisso meters, meters seem OK but bracket is bent. In other words, ONE BIG SHITSHOW.

December 27th (SR2528)

Tucker trawl in the morning, around 300m? followed by a dive around 11:00. the salps in tripours did not live through the night and the one salp in lloyds respiration experiment did not nearly reach Pcrit after 24hrs, we'll leave that one in. we broke down our respiration on Amphipods. Nick worked on the flowmeters overnight and reinforced the bracket. Everything is put back on the MOC and we will test the flowmeters tomorrow during calibration. Wireflyer and Vampire went in during the afternoon and evening followed by a Reeve net and squid jigging. 3 more squid were caught for Arminda and the reeve net deployment was successful going 12mpm down and 5 mpm up. No respirations were started from the reeve net on our end as all chambers were already running but Ana collected all she wanted from the bucket. After the Reevenet the Tucker went in for a deep trawl overnight.

December 28th (SR2528)

Tucker was retrieved about 7:00 in the morning followed by our MOCNESS calibration, conditions weren't perfect but the calibration was successful and both flowmeters are giving counts again, we are sticking with flowmeter 2 as primary as nick explained this is the one he was able to adjust best and is probably giving the most accurate counts. After the calibration we deployed the MOCNESS (MOC11) again for a fine scale tow targeting 525-

200m, entire tow was successful. MOCNESS was the last operation of this science leg and after retrieval we started steaming towards La Paz. Overnight conditions got rougher and we went down around 5 AM to double check if everything was secure and further tighten down all important equipment. Luckily all that was rolling around were sharpies and Styrofoam cups.

Date	Time	TC	CNF	FC	VOL	Pres	Temp	Cond	Salinity	Fluor	Trans	Oxy	Angle
251228	185600	1	1	361	1451.48	522.8	7.472	35.5517	34.562	0.02	95.92	-99	40.2
251228	190808	2	2	139	494.19	450.5	8.269	36.2777	34.588	0.01	95.85	-99	47.6
251228	192617	3	3	206	752.05	375.6	9.223	37.1719	34.633	0.02	95.83	0.016	49.6
251228	193150	4	4	67	241.93	350.6	9.525	37.4494	34.639	0.01	95.88	0.015	46.4
251228	193636	5	5	51	185.38	343.3	9.732	37.6493	34.65	0.02	95.83	0.019	47.7
251228	194413	6	6	84	313.66	299.9	10.471	38.3666	34.693	0.02	23.76	0.051	47.5
251228	194912	7	7	56	209.59	270.7	10.98	38.866	34.724	0.01	23.72	0.091	47.9
251228	195838	8	8	105	407.73	248.8	11.249	39.1311	34.744	0.01	23.65	0.12	42.8
251228	201340	9	9	182	682.02	149.7	13.408	41.3218	34.9	0	23.43	0.577	43.2
251228	203019	10	10	204	863.59	-0.3	17.112	0.0024	0.009	0	88.56	6.862	3.2

MOC 11-D

December 29th (SR2529)

Delayed arrival in La Paz, as expected, final docking happened around noon with all new science crew aboard by the deadline of 3 o'clock. No time to go onshore this time around.

We set sail around 4pm and started steaming slowly towards Carmen. Safety briefing was given around 18:00

CHANGE IN AUTHORSHIP! ALL PHOTOS STILL SEM/RO, TEXT MOSTLY NOW AMY.

December 30th (SR2529)

Steaming towards Carmen still slow. Drill at 1215. 1600 there was an accident in the gym with a personnel requiring stitches. We changed plans and came into Port in Guaymas around midnight to get stitches.

December 31st (SR2529)

Not released from port until 1600. Departed at 1700. Karaoke in the lounge with chocolate fondue and cheese plates for celebration. Reached Guaymas Basin ~2100. Tucker (#11) into the water for a shallow night tow (100 m). Successful tow: many squid, fish, phileroi, more pteropods than I have ever seen before in my life (diacavolinia, cavolinia, creseis, gymnosomes). Loki, then Reeve. Ball drop on the back deck at midnight. Yay New Years!!

January 1st (SR2529)

Set up respirations with copepods (Respiration 6!). Wire flier in around 100 and profiling all night. 8:00 morning dive followed by MOCNESS for Uriel (450m) followed by Vampire deployment. Not many fish in the MOC, but gave Uriel and Ana the whole sample. Broke down copepods respiration. Reeve net was deployed in the evening and 12 chaetognaths were selected for respirations. Many salps for Lloyd and some pteropods for Karson. Ship relocated to the same transect as previous wire flyer and an evening horizontal MOCNESS was done at 375m.

Row Labels	Average of oxygen	Max of oxygen	Min of oxygen
0	1.100262533	4.5579	0.1446
1	0.170654823	0.2053	0.1207
2	0.095119753	0.1345	0.0739
3	0.111065455	0.1579	0.0697
4	0.12343038	0.1716	0.0701
5	0.081527446	0.1442	0.0573
6	0.147331469	0.1589	0.1166
7	0.085987286	0.1209	0.0518
8	0.101552558	0.1462	0.0486
9	1.459899238	5.593	0.0655

January 2nd (SR2529)

Divers in the water 8 am. Wire flier 1000-1500. CTD to 800 m at 15:30 to collect water for respirations, and 450-surface to match ethanol preserved sampled from yesterdays MOCNESS. Brad took some samples for an ethanol assay that suggests there is a midwater peak in ethanol at 300 m. Cool stuff. Vampire went in autonomously at 14:30. It was not communicating well with the ship, but it came up when it was supposed to and was visible by light at night. Good recovery. Discovered that the issue was it was 6 lbs to heavy (easy fix). Broke down respiration experiment 7. Conducted a shallow Tucker Trawl to 300ish at 2000 - scattershot of interesting animals. Reeve net 0-100 right after. Set up myctophid excretion experiment. Lloyd got a few salps. Set up an ostracod respiration. Wire flier went in and stayed in overnight

January 3rd (SR2529)

Weather was not great for a dive, so the wire flier stayed in well past the daytime DVM to capture a few hours of daytime across an oxygen feature. At 11:30 the Tucker went in and trawled around 300 m. Right after the Tucker came onboard we did a surface Reeve (67.5 m).

Everyone received animals for experimentation from between those two tows. Switched out the Tucker for the MOCNESS and rinsed down the nets (there were a lot of residual organisms in Net 2 and Net 6 from last night, need to make a note of that!). Started steaming for Carmen. Broke down the respirations from last night. Arrived in Carmen 2030 and tossed the MOC into the water. Went down a little to sharp of an angle but came up beautifully.

Tow 9 (MOC14)
Night tow
Vertical
20:32- 00:23
01-04-26

Night tow
BV/BM
Vertical
20:32- 00:23
01-04-26

January 4th (SR2529)

Net to the surface at 0030. Started the biomass/ethanol/formalin processing pipeline. Amy and Ana to bed at 4, Ro and Sem stayed up to cock the nets. Vampire went in at 0200. Successfully completed one cycle - coms still not ideal, but perfectly followed the dive plan. Missed the second iteration window by 30 minutes. They are happy with the mission. 0800 Dive - cloudy similar taxon. Lots of pretty Cavolinia and Ctenophores. 1000 Ana sent the CTD (with styrofoam cups and snowmen) to +2000 m. Getting eDNA, water for Brad's ethanol analysis. MOC deployed at 1300 out at 1713. I was a little worried about how late we came up in the day, but we passed the migrator layer before they moved. Processing went very smooth. 1900 Tucker, 100 mwo, 75-60 mwo for most of the tow 50 mwo for 10- minutes. Beroe, krill, myctophids, salps. 2030 Reeve - beroe, diatoms, salps, phyleroie, ctenophore. 2130 LOKI. Vampire went in and did a nice solo dive. Wireflieer went for the remainder of the night.

MOC15, Net 1
1000-800m
VF=1591.9

MOC 15, Net 2
800-500m
VF=1770.2

MOC15, Net 3
500-350m
VF=1293.2

MOC15, Net 4
350-300m
VF=258.6

MOC15, Net 5
300-250m
VF=268.6

MOC15, Net 6
250-150m
VF=650

MOC15, Net 7
150-110m
VF=227.5

MOC15, Net 8
110-50
VF=413.5

MOC15, Net 9
50-0
VF=469.6

Tow 10 (MOC15)
Day tow
Vertical
12:59-?
01-04-26

MOC15, Net 1
1000-800m
VF=1591.9

MOC 15, Net 2
800-500m
VF=1770.2

MOC15, Net 3
500-350m
VF=1293.2

MOC15, Net 4
350-300m
VF=258.6

MOC15, Net 5
300-250m
VF=268.6

MOC15, Net 6
250-150m
VF=650

No Pic?

MOC15, Net 7
150-110m
VF=227.5

MOC15, Net 8
110-50
VF=413.5

MOC15, Net 9
50-0
VF=469.6

Tow 9 (MOC14)
Night tow
BV/BM
Vertical
20:32- ?
01-04-26

January 5th (SR2529)

0800 dive. Lena got the “not phyleroie” that she has been looking for.

Thliptodon, Pneumoderma, Pneumodermopsis. Two kinds of Cavolinia (one rounder with yellow trailers, one more laterally compressed with white trailers), HUGE Corolla.

1000 LOKI, a bit too much jelly to feel like the net was quantitative. Steam back to coordinates from the WF team and horizontal MOCNESS at 250 m starting at 1130. We got down to depth really fast and then we were a bit ahead of our planned route. The currents had shifted the feature beyond where it was predicted. HOWEVER! We held strong and the feature showed up just 30 minutes after the predicted lat/long. The community was relatively consistent across the 250 depth (so many ostracods and clio pyramidata).

Since the volume filtered was so variable it is hard to say if there were differences. We will see once we scan. 1730 GORGEOUS sunset with dolphins. Moved the MOC to be ready for the Tucker trawl. The Tucker went in at 1910 lots of beroe, fish, big krill, salps. Variety pack of cephalopods (six species?). Reeve went in a 2020 and was chock full of diatoms and siphonophores (gross). Got some salps. LOKI in 2100ish. Vampire went in overnight. Poor comms, despite the fact they fiddled with one of the settings (makes worse acoustics but they thought it would help. It did not). Its doing what it is supposed to do though!!

MOC16, Net 1
250m
VF=1928.4

MOC 16, Net 2
250m
VF=1114.1

MOC16, Net 3
250m
VF=444.9

MOC16, Net 4
250m
VF=1781.6

MOC16, Net 5
250m
VF=2284.4

MOC16, Net 6
250m,
VF=259.6

MOC16, Net 7
250m,
VF= 150.1

MOC16, Net 8
250m,
VF= 519.9

Tow 9 (MOC16)
Day tow
horizontal
11:41 ?
01-05-26

January 6th (SR2529)

0800 dive. Lena got her not phyleroie, a salp. Reeve at 1000. Broke down Experiment 11. Amy and Ro started playing with the horizontal tow data from last year. STUFF HAPPENED AND I DID NOT WRITE IT DOWN! Three reeve nets? Way less diatoms which made it a salp bonanza. There was a Tucker trawl too? I think this is when Tim made the first copper plate - its a pteropod!!!! And the next one is going to be a pteropod too!! I am contaminating one artist at a time (they are stupidly beautiful out here and crazy abundant)!!!!!!!

January 7th (SR2529)

800 dive, 1000 Reeve, 11000 Loki. Everyone had fun setting up their last round of experiments (Sem and Ro did a scattershot for Experiment 12, Karson did a few more pteropods). Headed to port! Ro and Sem broke down Experiment 12 at midnight then left everything out to dry so it is ready to send to Lauren tomorrow morning.

January 8th (SR2529)

Amy got up at 700 and packed the respiration kit and Georig for Lauren. The respiration box and the computer went to URI with Lindsay. 800 two small boats arrived to allow science and crew to unload. Some crew arrived first. First boat was filled with samples and gear (and Uriel). Everything was handed over the side. It was...not ideal, but we did it as safely and carefully as possible. The second boat took all science and their luggage. Everyone was gone by 900. It was a little rushed and disorganized but seemed ok. Some crew offloaded and the customs team arrived. At this juncture we realized there had been a failure in communication and the bridge was unaware that one of the science party was NOT transiting back to San Diego. There were multiple points where communication had apparently failed. We tried to get the person back to the boat but the agent was unable to find a way to get the person from La Paz to Pichilingue before customs closed at 1800. The boat was released and started heading back to San Diego. My take home on the life lessons - Be SURE the list of people transiting is clearly communicated. It is a BIG DEAL. If you hire a boat, remember that you paid them and its ok for them to have to wait for you to complete an orderly check out. Main lesson - slow down. We did not need to rush (we were not really inconveniencing anyone). Because we rushed we missed some failchecks in the system. No one's fault, but lots of people felt really bad about it all.

January 9th (SR2601)

Started cleaning up the lab space around 1030. Ana coordinated with the bridge to add some stops for a CTD along the way north (to collect eDNA). Got the lat/longs and Nick started to remake the CTD termination. Stopped for lunch and a safety drill (they pretended the dive locker was on fire and practiced using the fire hoses - very fun. We hung out in the lab and chatted about life). Took apart the MOCNESS nets for Lynn Butler. Had a mishap where the hatch on the back deck was not sealed and the bucket we were using to wash the nets was leaking and we flooded the bosun's locker. This was ... unfortunate. Fixed the hatch and the bucket and then lost Nick to swabbing out the locker for a minute. Tim made new choices for the final pieces of art and started rocking another plate. Ro and Sem started cleaning up Lloyd and our stuff. Karson emptied the waterbaths and started organizing Brad's stuff. Soaked the nets, stomped them clean and suspended them above the fantail. Wind kicked up A LOT after we rounded the tip of Baja, had to take down the nets (which are not as clean as I would have liked them to be) and locked down the deck. Everyone headed in to acclimate to the new sea state. No one is puking but most people have taken Dramamine.

January 10th (SR2601)

Deck secured. Everyone mostly hunkered in. The oarfish larvae died :(Had a FANTASTIC engine tour after lunch. Did a hummingbird/butterfly puzzle. It was decided that we would not stop to do eDNA sampling on the way north. The respiration gear was passed off in Rhode Island and Lauren is on her way to the Indian Ocean!

January 11th (SR2601)

Still wavy. Everyone mostly has gotten accustomed to the new motion. Epoxy plankton jewelry projects are underway. Tim made the salp sketch on the black painted copper plate. Next copper plate is ready? Its going to be the acantharia?? Hes stitching together a movie of all the cool ship stuff - plan is for about 15 minutes for a teaching audience (Lloyd or my intro classes). He might make a short version for instagram. I'm THRILLED. Phronema died BUT the babies hatched.

January 12th (SR2601)

GORGEOUS DAY. Apparently there were whales being all charismatic, but I was busy being in a zoom. Boo. Lots of the remaining stuff was put away (Karsen got all the waterbaths stowed and locked down a great deal of the remaining Seibel stuff. Broke down the Reeve net and did a SUPER thorough wash. We pulled the MOC nets out and what I had been concerned about mainly had turned into "zooplankton dandruff" over the past few days. With a lot of shaking it was pretty spotless. Tim has spent a ton of his time doing a highlights reel of all the science and its FREAKING COOL! We had a few showings and provided feedback and its going to be a phenomenal teaching resource. Found out we were arriving in San Diego a whole day early and we are all revisiting our travel plans.

January 13th (SR2601)

Land ho! We cleared all the customs/immigration/agriculture at 823. While science moseyed the ship went into hyperdrive and by the time we realized it EVERYTHING was pretty much on dry land from the back deck (before lunch!!). Sem got the rental car and then science went on an art adventure (unless they had teaching/learning obligations) then we met some Scripps people for drinks (Decima, Petrik), then the ZoopGroup lab went out for Dumplings (Meet Dumplings - had made - holy crap. Go here!).

January 14th (SR2601)

Zoopgroup went on a rampage to make sure Sem and Ro could leave today. Fedex of fish DOC samples to UCSB, drop XP machine back to Mark Omand at SIO, bought a new toolbox to store remaining gear, profit. Ana and Tim to get Tintypes (!!!). Packed the car. Waved goodbye. Called 6 minutes later because we forgot the frozen and formalin samples (THANK YOU AMBER). Packed the samples sheepishly. Waved goodbye. Roy took Amy to the airport at 1600. To the children!!

Fin.